

CRYSTALLINITY AND INTERPHASE PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBRE/PEEK MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The influence of thermal history on interfacial properties of carbon fibre reinforced poly(etheretherketone) (PEEK) matrix composites was studied. The fibre fragmentation and pull-out tests were used to measure the interfacial shear strength (IFSS). The correlations between IFSS, degree of crystallinity, morphology, and failure mechanisms were established. It is shown that the amorphous PEEK-rich interphase introduced in fast-cooled specimens or those crystallised at a low isothermal temperature resulted in ductile interface failures along with a low IFSS, whereas the transcrySTALLINE interphase obtained for slow-cooled specimens or those crystallised at a high isothermal temperature gave rise to a high IFSS with brittle interface debonding. The dependence of the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) on thermal history is explained by the transition of failure mechanisms, which are in turn controlled by the interphase morphology, ductility and IFSS.

KEYWORDS: Carbon fibre/PEEK composite, cooling rate, isothermal crystallisation, degree of crystallinity, interfacial shear strength, failure mechanism.

INTRODUCTION

Optimization of the mechanical properties of semicrystalline thermoplastic matrix composites requires fundamental understanding of the effect of processing conditions, particularly the thermal history, on the interface characteristics and matrix properties. The cooling rate and isothermal crystallisation temperature are dominant factors controlling the IFSS, but there is no consensus regarding their effects. Previous studies, for example, on glass fibre/polypropylene (PP) [2] and carbon fibre /polycarbonate (PC) [1] systems showed that increasing cooling rate improved the IFSS, arguably due to the improved wetting behaviour, high ductility, fracture energy and residual stresses, as well as the inhibition of molecular weight segregation or weak boundary layer. There were, however, reports for carbon fibre/PP [3], carbon fibre/polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) [4], carbon fibre/polyethylene terephthalate (PET) [5] and alumina fibre/PP [6] systems, showing little influence or even a completely opposite trend with cooling rate. The high IFSS with decreasing cooling rate was partly attributed to the formation of transcrySTALLINE interphase and better adsorption.

The major objectives of this study were to measure the interfacial mechanical properties of carbon fibre/PEEK composites as affected by thermal history of the composite, as well as to evaluate the roles of matrix crystallinity and interface morphology for the transition of interphase failure mechanisms.

EXPERIMENTAL

The Hercules AS4 carbon fibres, Victrex PEEK powder, and APC-2 prepreps (with continuous AS4 carbon fibres of 61% by volume) were used throughout the study. 16 layer laminates were fabricated using a hot press at a pressure of 1.38 MPa for 30 min. The mould was heated to 400 °C, followed by cooling between polyimide films and aluminium sheets at different cooling rates. A Datapaq tracker with thermocouples embedded in the specimen was used to measure the temperature profile during cooling. The mechanical properties of PEEK were measured in tension at a cross-head speed of 10 mm/min. The degree of crystallinity of both neat PEEK and carbon/PEEK composites were determined using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC). The specimens for single fibre pull-out and fragmentation tests were prepared by embedding a carbon fibre within the PEEK powder, which was in turn contained in a mould [7]. The specimen was heated to 400 °C in an oven, which was then allowed to cool at different cooling rates under the same procedures as the laminate composites or subjected to an isothermal crystallisation process. The pull-out and fragmentation experiments were performed on a Minimat microtensometer with a cross-head speed of 0.1 mm/min and 10 mm/min, respectively. The fibre fragment length and debond mechanisms were simultaneously monitored using a polarised light microscope, a video recorder and an image analysis unit. The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) was calculated from the maximum load divided by the nominal embedded fibre surface area.

Table 1: The effect of cooling rate on the crystallisation behaviour of PEEK and carbon/PEEK composites

Cooling Rate (°C/min)	T _c (°C)	T _m (°C)	ΔH _c (J/g)	ΔH _m (J/g)	Crystallinity (%)
1	-	351 (346)	-	49 [42]	38 [33]
70	-	351 (344)	-	38 [36]	30 [28]
160	-	352	-	37	28
600	188 (182)	352 (342)	3 [3]	37 [36]	26 [25]
1000	187	352	13	38	19
1500	188 (183)	351 (342)	14 [15]	36 [31]	17 [12]

* The values in parentheses () represent those for carbon/PEEK composites, and the values in parentheses [] are calculated taking into account the matrix weight fraction of 32% for carbon/PEEK composites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PEEK Bulk Matrix and Fibre/Matrix Interphase Properties

Typical engineering stress-strain curves of neat PEEKs processed at varying cooling rates are presented in Fig. 1. Both the modulus and yield strength of PEEK decreased while the ductility increased with increasing the cooling rate. This was expected because a high degree of crystallinity

with ordered crystallites and molecular perfection obtained at a slow-cooling rate gave rise to stiffness of the material, while making yielding difficult with dramatically reduced ductility. Distinct stress drops were observed after the yield point for specimens processed at cooling rates above 1000 °C/min. The absence of such stress drops in specimens crystallised at lower cooling rates seems associated with the post-yield hardening behaviour as a result of thick lamellae structure as often observed in annealed specimens [8].

The DSC data for the neat PEEK and carbon/PEEK composites processed at different cooling rates are summarised in Table 1. The degree of crystallinity decreased as the cooling rate increased for both materials, which is attributed to a decrease in the mobility of polymer chains, thus limiting the ability of the chains to diffuse into the growing crystal fronts [9]. It is interesting to note that both the degree of crystallinity and the melting temperature for neat PEEK were slightly higher than those for the composites processed at the same cooling rate. In particular, an increase in cooling rate resulted in a marginal decrease in melting temperature for the composite, whereas there was virtually no effect for the neat PEEK, as reported previously for carbon fibre/PPS composites [9]. The scanning electron micrograph of the etched surface, as illustrated in Figure 2, indicates that the presence of fibre influences the nucleation and growth of spherulites in the surrounding PEEK matrix. It appears that the spherulites preferentially nucleate from the fibre surface, and impinge quickly on each other as they emerge radially [10]. Such fibre-nucleated transcrystallisation would particularly be expected from highly graphitised carbon fibres when processed at a slow-cooling rate or in an isothermal cooling condition, and is distinguishable from the shear-induced cylindrical structure via homogeneous nucleation [11].

Table 2: Weibull modulus m , scale parameter l_0 and mean fibre fragmentation length of specimens with different cooling rates

Cooling Rate (°C/min)	Weibull modulus m	Weibull scale parameter l_0 (mm)	Mean fibre fragmentation length (mm)
490	2.88	0.40	0.35
600	2.81	0.49	0.43
1000	3.55	0.53	0.47
1500	3.16	0.55	0.49
1800	2.91	0.61	0.54

The cumulative frequency plots of fibre fragment length obtained from the single fibre fragmentation tests are shown in Fig. 3. A summary of the corresponding mean fibre fragmentation length, Weibull modulus and scale parameters calculated by the two-parameter Weibull distribution analysis are presented in Table 2. The mean fibre fragmentation length generally increased with increasing cooling rate, a clear indication of reduced interface bond quality and hence the efficiency of stress transfer across the interface. Meanwhile, the Weibull modulus, m , varied irregularly with the cooling rate without exhibiting any general trend, indicating that the scattering of fibre fragment length was insensitive to cooling rate. In addition, the elastic modulus of matrix material has also shown to be an important parameter dictating the fibre fragmentation phenomenon.

Fig. 1 Representative stress-strain profiles of PEEK with different cooling rates.

Fig. 3 Fibre fragment length distributions observed in fragmentation test in AS4/PEEK specimens with different cooling rates.

Fig. 2 Scanning electron micrograph of permanganic etched cross-section of slowly cooled [0/45] AS4/PEEK laminates.

Fig. 4 Variations of IFSS, ILSS and degree of crystallinity with cooling rate.

The IFSS values obtained from the single fibre pull-out test are presented in Fig. 4 along with the results from the short beam shear and DSC tests. It is interesting to note that the increase of cooling rate from 1 °C/min to about 600 °C/min resulted in a significant reduction in all properties measured, including IFSS, interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and the degree of crystallinity. Further increase of cooling rate beyond 600 °C/min did not much vary the IFSS and ILSS while the degree of crystallinity decreased further. It is also worth highlighting that the IFSS values exceeded the shear strength of the neat PEEK resin and were even approximately equivalent to the corresponding tensile strengths (105 MPa and 70 MPa for specimens processed at cooling rates of 1 °C/min and 1500 °C/min, respectively). All the foregoing observations suggest that the fibres were strongly bonded to the surrounding transcrystalline interphase layer which had a higher modulus than the bulk matrix. It seems that there was a maximum cooling rate above which the formation of transcrystalline layer was rather difficult, resulting in an amorphous PEEK-rich interphase around the carbon fibre. The critical value is thought to be roughly 400~600 °C/min in view of the sharp changes in the interface properties, IFSS and ILSS at these cooling rates.

Fig. 5 IFSS versus degree of crystallinity for different non-isothermal and isothermal crystallization conditions.

A further study was made of the effects of isothermal crystallisation temperature and holding time on the interface parameters, and the fibre pull-out test results are presented in Fig. 5. In general, the IFSS varied roughly proportional to the degree of crystallinity for all processing conditions studied. The higher the isothermal crystallisation temperature and the longer the isothermal holding time were, the higher was the degree of crystallinity and hence the IFSS. It seems that a treatment at a high isothermal temperature gave rise to more complete crystallisation with a thick lamella structure having an ameliorating effect on interface bond, while a treatment at a low isothermal temperature resulted in self-seeding nucleation, which in turn limited the size of transcryallites and spherulites. It is also noted that the IFSS values for annealed specimens were lower than those for isothermally or non-isothermally crystallised specimens having the same degree of crystallinity. This result indicates that the annealing process tended to increase the degree of crystallinity preferentially in the form of imperfect spherulites with small lamellar structure mainly in the bulk matrix, whereas the slow cooling and isothermal treatment encouraged more transcryallisation at the interphase region.

Failure Behaviour

SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces and schematic diagrams of failure mechanisms are presented in Fig. 6. The slow-cooled specimens with a strong interfacial bond exhibited mainly a cohesive failure as evidenced by the thick layer of PEEK covering the whole fibre surface with extensive matrix deformation. Since the transcryalline layers in the slow-cooled specimens consisted essentially of radially oriented crystalline lamellae that were bonded strongly to the fibre surface (see Fig. 2), fracture tended to occur through the formation of interlamellar cracks running both parallel and perpendicular to the fibre axis, as shown in Fig. 6(a). In sharp contrast, the fast-cooled specimen failed apparently by the combined adhesive and cohesive failure mechanisms (Fig. 6(b)). The weakly bonded interface tended to fail prematurely before the capacity of the ductile amorphous-rich PEEK matrix to deform plastically was fully utilised.

Fig. 6 SEM fracture surfaces and schematic failure process of short beam shear tested carbon/PEEK laminates cooled at (a) 1 °C/min, and (b) 2000 °C/min.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of thermal history on the interfacial bond strength and failure mechanisms of carbon/PEEK composites has been studied, and the following conclusions can be drawn:

- (a) The presence of fibre influences the nucleation and growth of spherulites in the surrounding PEEK matrix.
- (b) The cooling rate and isothermal treatment are the major parameters that dictate the degree of crystallinity and the IFSS. The slower the cooling rate, the higher the isothermal crystallisation temperature and the longer the isothermal holding time are, the higher are the degree of crystallinity and thus the IFSS.
- (c) The interphase failure mechanisms depend on both the mechanical properties and crystallinity of matrix material. The amorphous PEEK-rich interphase introduced in fast-cooled specimens results in a combined adhesive and cohesive interface failure and a low IFSS, whereas the transcrystalline interphase in slow-cooled specimens gives rise to a high IFSS with mainly cohesive interphase debonding.

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